

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

ESTIMATION OF PHYTOCONSTITUENTS AND COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF ANTI-OBESITY ACTIVITY OF AYURVEDIC AND HOMEOPATHIC MEDICINES IN HIGH FAT DIET ANIMAL MODEL

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 11/03/2018

Available online
31/03/2018

Keywords

HFCD,
Obesity,
Phytolacca Berry,
Stholyantak Churna.

ABSTRACT

The objective of the study is to assess the anti-obesity activity of ayurvedic and homeopathic formulations namely Stholyantak churna and Phytolacca berry in high fat cafeteria diet induced obesity (HFCD). Obesity was induced by administration of HFCD for a period of 42 days and both the formulations were given for 42 days. Administration of HFCD significantly increased the body weight and organ weights. Hepatic marker enzymes such as ALT, ALP and AST levels were increased and HDL level was decreased in HFCD control group compared to normal group. Treatment with formulations showed a significant reduction in the body weight gain, organ weight of the liver, kidney, spleen. Levels of hepatic enzymes and lipid profile were restored. The total phenolic content of the Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna was found to be 31.16 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 70.39 $\mu\text{g/g}$. The total flavonoid content of the Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna was found to be 12.28 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 41.36 $\mu\text{g/g}$. Chemical investigation of Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna led to identify the flavonoids quercetin and phenols gallic acid were present in formulations by HPTLC technique along with standard markers. The HPTLC fingerprinting of formulations revealed the presence of the 0.04% of gallic acid in Phytolacca berry, Stholyantak churna in aqueous showed 0.47% of gallic acid and Stholyantak churna in methanol showed 0.08% of quercetin and 0.03% of gallic acid. Based on the above results, it was concluded that the ayurvedic and homeopathic formulations, Stholyantak churna and Phytolacca berry possess significant anti-obesity activity in HFCD induced obesity model. Stholyantak churna possess higher anti-obesity activity than Phytolacca berry.

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Please cite this article in press as **Arivukkarasu Ramasamy et al.** Estimation of Phytoconstituents and Comparative Evaluation of Anti-Obesity Activity of Ayurvedic and Homeopathic Medicines in High Fat Diet Animal Model. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(03).

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INTRODUCTION

Obesity is defined as a condition of abnormal or excessive fat accumulation in the human body beyond the amount required for the normal body function. This continuous accumulation has a result of weight gain that may impair the health. It is a risk factor in cardiovascular disease, hypertension, pulmonary disease, non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus, arthritis, cancers (breast, uterus and colon), varicose veins and gallbladder disease [1-2]. Obesity is assessed by body mass index (BMI). BMI is a mathematical formula that is defined by body weight in Kg/ Height in meter². Overweight is defined as a BMI of 25 to 29.9 kg/m² and obesity as a BMI of ≥ 30 kg/m² [3]. The 21st century finds many people using more natural, less drug-oriented therapies, because more aware of limitations and adverse effects of modern medicines. The natural remedies work, often better than prescription drugs for many health conditions. Ayurveda is "science of life", it maintaining optimal health and mitigating disease by using ayurvedic medicines is the goal of Ayurveda. Homeopathy (Homeo-similar, Pathy-suffering) "Principle of similar" and "principle of dilution" are the two basic principles used in homeopathic treatments. Stholyantak churna is an ayurvedic polyherbal formulation is useful in detoxify the digestive system, reduce fatty deposits, improves blood circulation, hypothyroidism, corrects carbohydrate and protein metabolism and reduces weight naturally [4]. Phytolacca berry is homeopathic formulation used in the treatment of thyroid disorders, metabolic problems, overweight due to deposition of fat in their muscles, hormonal imbalance, burning extra fat [5].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Procurement of formulations:

Phytolacca berry tablet contains 20% of the Phytolacca berry extract. It is manufactured by Dr. Willmar Schwabe India Pvt. Ltd. (Noida, India). It was procured from Sree Ayush Agencies, Coimbatore. Stholyantak churna was manufactured by herbal company, Punjab.

Preparation of sample:

Phytolacca berry tablets was dissolved in distilled water and then filtered. The filtrate was used for further study. Stholyantak churna (1 tablespoon-14.3gm) was added into 400ml water. Boil until it is concentrated to 50ml, which was then cooled and filtered. The filtrate used for further study.

QUALITATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

The following preliminary phytochemical investigations of Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna were performed by the standard methods (Harborne, 1973; Markham, 1982; Kokate, 1994) [6-8].

QUANTIFICATION OF TOTAL PHENOLICS AND FLAVONOIDS

Estimation of total phenolic content

Preparation of standard:

Standard solution was prepared by adding 10mg of accurately weighed Gallic acid in 10ml of distilled water.

Preparation of sample:

10mg of the accurately weighed samples were separately dissolved in 10ml water and used for the estimation.

Procedure:

The total phenolic content of the samples was determined by Folin-Ciocalteu assay method. To an aliquot 100 μ l of both samples (1mg/ml) and standard solution of Gallic acid (10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 μ g/ml) were added, 50 μ l of Folin-ciocalteu reagent followed by 860 μ l of distilled water and the mixture was incubated for 5mins at room temperature. 100 μ l of 20% sodium carbonate and 890 μ l of distilled water were added to make the final solution to 2ml. It was incubated for 30min in dark to complete the reaction. After that absorbance of the mixture was measured at 725nm against blank. Distilled water was used as the reagent blank. The tests were performed in triplicate to get the mean values. The total phenolic content was found out from the calibration curve of Gallic acid. And it was expressed as milligrams of Gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of samples.

Estimation of total flavonoid content

Preparation of standard:

Standard solution was prepared by adding 10mg of accurately weighed quercetin in 10ml of ethanol.

Preparation of sample:

10mg of the accurately weighed samples were separately dissolved in 10ml water and used for the estimation.

Procedure:

The total flavonoid content of the samples was determined by using Aluminium chloride colorimetric method. To an aliquot of 100 μ l of both samples (1mg/ml) or standard solutions of quercetin (10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 μ g/ml), ethanol was added separately to make up the solution up to 2ml. The resulting mixture was treated with 0.1ml of 10% aluminium chloride, 0.1ml of 1M potassium acetate and 2.8ml of distilled water. The mixture was shaken well and incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes. The absorbance was measured at 415nm against blank, where a solution of 2ml ethanol, 0.1ml potassium acetate, 2.8 ml distilled water and 0.1ml of aluminium chloride serve as the blank solution. The total flavonoid content was determined from the standard quercetin calibration curve and it was expressed as milligrams of Quercetin equivalents (QE) per gram of samples [9].

HPTLC ANALYSIS

Preparation of standard:

1mg of quercetin, rutin and gallic acid were dissolved in 1ml of methanol (HPTLC grade). 5µl of each standard were spotted on the HPTLC plate.

Preparation of sample:

Phytolacca berry tablets (Each tablet contained 20% of the Phytolacca berry extract) was used for the study. Stholyantak churna (1 tablespoon-14.3gm) was added into 400ml of water. Boil the mixture it is concentrated to 50ml, which was then cooled and filtered. The filtrate was dried, from this take 2gm dissolved in 10ml of water. Sonicate it for 10mins. Sample was then filtered by using Whatman No.1 filter paper. 200mg of Stholyantak churna was dissolved in 2ml of methanol. 10µl of samples were spotted on the HPTLC plate.

Selection of chromatographic layer:

The precoated plate of Merck silica gel G 60 F254 was used for this study.

Mobile phase:

The widespread of mobile phase used for detection and estimation of flavonoids and phenolic acid were Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Formic acid: Methanol (3:6:1.6:0.4) mentioned [10].

Procedure:

High performance thin layer chromatography was performed using CAMAG HPTLC using WINCATS 1.4.3 application software and scanning. The standards quercetin, rutin and gallic acid(5µl) samples were spotted in form of bands with a Camag microlitre syringe on pre-coated Silica Gel glass plate 60F₂₅₄ (10×10cm with 0.2mm thickness) using a Camag Linomat 5 applicator. The plates were pre-washed with methanol and activated at 60⁰c for 10min prior to chromatography. The sample loaded plate was kept in TLC twin trough developing chamber after chamber saturation with respective mobile phase. The optimized chamber saturation time for mobile phase was 5 min at room temperature. Linear ascending development was carried out and the plate was developed in the respective mobile phase up to 7cm. The developed plate was then dried by hot air to evaporate solvents from the plate and also for the development of bands. The dried plate was observed under UV light at 254nm and 366nm and photo documentation was done. Before densitometric scanning, plates were heated for 5 min in oven at 105°C. Densitometric evaluation of the plates was performed at λ=254 nm & 366 nm using a CAMAG Scanner III with tungsten lamp in conjunction with WINCATS software for quantitation [11].

PHARMACOLOGICAL STUDY

Experimental animal:

Wistar mice, 20-22g body weight were procured from the animal house of KMCH College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu. All the mice were housed and maintained under standard conditions of temperature (25°C ± 5°C), relative humidity (55 ± 10%), and 12/12 h light/dark cycles in the animal house. All the mice were provided with standard commercial pellet diet and water *ad libitum* freely throughout the study. Protocol for the study was approved by the institutional animal ethical committee (IAEC) for animal care and were in accordance with committee for the purpose of control and supervision of experiments on animals (CPCSEA) guidelines, Government of India.

ACUTE TOXICITY STUDY

Acute oral toxicity study was performed as per the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) OECD-423 guidelines. The mice were fasted overnight with free access of water and were grouped into three groups of 3 animals each, to which the samples was administered orally at the dose of 50mg/kg, 500mg/kg and 2000mg/kg body weight. After the administration of test substance, food was withheld for 2hrs but not water. All the animals were observed individually after administration for the first 30 minutes and periodically during the first 24hrs, with special attention given during the first 4hrs, and daily thereafter, for a total period of 14days. Animals were observed for gross behavioural and morphological profiles in this period [12].

High fat cafeteria diet induced obesity

Cafeteria diet consisted of 3 diets 1) 40g of condensed milk and 40g of bread, 2) 15g of chocolates, 30g of biscuits and 30g of dried coconuts, 3) 40g of cheese and 50g of boiled potatoes. These 3 diets provided to 6 mice in each group for 42 days. These diets were provided in addition to normal pellet chow.

Experimental Design

Mice were divided into five groups of six animals each.

- Group I : Normal group received standard chow diet for 42 days.
- Group II : Obesity control group received high fat cafeteria diet only for 42 days.
- Group III : Mice fed with HFCD along with standard drug Orlistat (50mg/kg body weight, p.o) for 42 days.
- Group IV : Treatment group received HFCD along with Phytolacca berry (1.95mg/20gm of mice, p.o) for 42 days.
- Group V : Treatment group received HFCD along with Stholyantak churna (7.15mg/20gm of mice, p.o) for 42 days [13].

Sample collection and Biochemical Analysis

The changes in body weight of the animals were observed in all groups. The blood samples were collected via retro orbital puncture from overnight fasted animals on 42th day. Animals were sacrificed by cervical dislocation. The blood samples were kept at room temperature for 10-15 min and centrifuged using cooling centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 5 min. serum was separated and used for various biochemical analyses. The liver, kidney, spleen were dissected out, washed in normal saline, blotted dry and weighed. Lipid profile TC, TG, HDL, LDL, VLDL and biochemical parameters ALT, ALP, AST levels were evaluated.

PARAMETERS EVALUATION

Estimation of serum biochemical and lipid parameters

The serum was analysed for biochemical parameters such as alanine transaminase, alkaline phosphatase, aspartate transaminase, total cholesterol, triglyceride and high density lipoprotein according to standard method using the semi auto analyser (photometer 5010 v₅₊) with enzymatic kits (Piramal health care limited, Coral clinical systems) [14-20].

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data were analysed by one way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test using Graphpad 5.0 software. The values were expressed as mean \pm SEM. P<0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

QUALITATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Preliminary phytochemical analysis of formulations such as Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna showed the presence of Carbohydrates, glycosides, phenols, tannins, flavonoids, triterpenoids, sterols and saponins.

QUANTIFICATION OF TOTAL PHENOLS AND FLAVONOIDS

Total phenolic content was determined by using the Folin-ciocalteu (FC) reagent method. The total phenolic content of the Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna was found to be 31.16 μ g/g and 70.39 μ g/g. The total flavonoid content of the Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna was found to be 12.28 μ g/g and 41.36 μ g/g. (Table 1).

Table 1: The total phenolic content and total flavonoid content in formulations.

Sample	Total phenol content μ g/g of GAE	Total flavonoid content μ g/g of QE
Phytolacca berry	31.16 μ g/g	12.28 μ g/g
Stholyantak churna	70.39 μ g/g	41.36 μ g/g

ESTIMATION OF PHYTOCONSTITUENTS BY HPTLC

HPTLC study was carried out for the quantification of phytoconstituents in formulations. Toluene: ethyl acetate: formic acid: methanol in the ratio of 3:6:1.6:0.4 gave better elution for formulations tested and hence it was used as mobile phase for detection of constituents in formulations. After development the plate was scanned in densitometer under 254nm and the chromatogram obtained is depicted in figure (Table 2) (Fig. 1-8).

Figure 1: HPTLC profile of formulations at 254nm

Figure 2: 3D display of HPTLC chromatogram of Samples and Standards

1. Phytolacca berry,
2. Stholyantak churna aqueous
3. Stholyantak churna methanol
4. Quercetin, 5. Rutin, 6. Gallic acid

Figure 3: Chromatogram of Phytolacca berry

Figure 4: Chromatogram of Stholyantak churna in aqueous

Figure 5: Chromatogram of Stholyantak churna in methanol

Figure 6: Chromatogram of Standard marker quercetin

Figure 7: Chromatogram of standard marker rutin

Figure 8: Chromatogram of standard marker gallic acid

Table2: R_f values and area of marker compounds and the constituents in formulations.

Markers	R _f value			Area			% of marker in formulation				
	Std	A	B	C	Std	A	B	C	A	B	C
Gallic acid	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.66	19932.3	1891.1	19110.5	1117.5	0.04%	0.47%	0.03%
Quercetin	0.80	-	-	0.80	15207.9	-	-	2598.8	-	-	0.08%

A-Phytolacca berry, B-Stholyantak churna in aqueous, C- Stholyantak churna in methanol

ACUTE TOXICITY TEST

Single oral administration of Stholyantak churna at a dose of 50mg/kg, 500mg/kg and 2000mg/kg as per OECD-423 guidelines for 14 days did not produce any mortality in tested animals. No observable signs of toxicity was detected during the experimental period.

SCREENING OF ANTI-OBESITY ACTIVITY

Effect of samples on body weight and organ weight

After 42 days of HFCD administration, body weight and organ weight increased significantly in HFCD obesity control group as compared with normal group which were fed with normal pellet chow. Treated with Phytolacca berry (1.95mg/20gm of mice) and Stholyantak churna (7.15mg/20gm of mice) showed a significant decrease in body weight gain and organ weight [13]. (Table 3, 4), (Fig. 9-13).

Table3: Effect of Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna on body weight gain in HFCD induced obesity.

Day	Normal (saline)	Control (HFCD only)	Standard	Phytolacca berry	Stholyantak churna
Day 0	26.17 ± 0.70	23.83 ± 0.60 ^{ns}	24.33 ± 0.42 ^{ns}	27.33 ± 0.49 ^b	27.67 ± 0.56 ^a
Day 42	25.67 ± 0.66	32.50 ± 0.67 ^a	27.17 ± 0.60 ^a	29.17 ± 0.31 ^b	26.33 ± 0.61 ^a

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM; (n=6); (p<0.0001, ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparison test). Control vs. Normal. Standard and Test groups vs. Control. (a=***p<0.0001, b=**p<0.001, c=*p<0.05, ns-non significant).

Figure9: Effect of Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna on body weight in HFCD induced obesity.

Table 4: Effect of Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna on organ weight in HFCD induced obesity.

Groups	Liver	Spleen	Kidney L	Kidney R
Normal	1.09±	0.13±	0.17±	0.22±
Control (HFCD)	1.32±	0.19±	0.22±	0.25±
Standard	1.18±	0.15±	0.17±	0.22±
Phytolacca berry (Sample 1)	1.21±	0.16±	0.19±	0.23±
Stholyantak churna (Sample 2)	1.09±	0.14±	0.15±	0.21±
	0.021	0.010	0.001	0.003
	0.031 ^a	0.005 ^a	0.003 ^a	0.006 ^a
	0.020 ^b	0.007 ^b	0.004 ^a	0.002 ^a
	0.021 ^b	0.006 ^c	0.004 ^b	0.005 ^b
	0.011 ^a	0.007 ^a	0.005 ^a	0.002 ^a

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM; (n=6); (p<0.0001, ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparison test). Control vs. Normal. Standard and Test groups vs. Control. (a=***p<0.0001, b=**p<0.001, c=*p<0.05, ns-non significant).

Figure 10: Effect of samples on liver weight

Figure 11: Effect of samples on spleen weight

Figure 12: Effect of samples on kidney L weight

Figure 13: Effect of samples on kidney R weight

Effect of samples on serum biochemical parameters

Hepatic enzymes such as alanine transaminase, alkaline phosphatase and aspartate transaminase levels were increased in HFCD control group compared to normal group received chow pellet whereas, the levels of AST, ALT and ALP significantly reduced in treatment with Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna [12]. (Table 5), (Fig. 15-17).

Table5: Effect of Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna on serum biochemical parameters in HFCD induced obesity.

Groups	ALT (U/L)	ALP (U/L)	AST (U/L)
Normal	30.67 ± 2.60	86.67 ± 6.69	36.47 ± 0.79
Control(HFCD)	66.67 ± 2.19 ^a	155.3 ± 4.91 ^a	81.00 ± 2.65 ^a
Standard	50.00 ± 0.58 ^b	106.3 ± 3.84 ^b	56.00 ± 3.22 ^a
Phytolacca berry (Sample 1)	54.67 ± 0.88 ^c	118.0 ± 9.87 ^c	64.67 ± 2.03 ^b
Stholyantak churna (Sample 2)	50.33 ± 2.73 ^b	91.33 ± 2.73 ^a	53.67 ± 2.40 ^a

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM; (n=6); (p<0.0001, ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparison test). Control vs. Normal. Standard and Test groups vs. Control. (a=***p<0.0001, b=**p<0.001, c=*p<0.05, ns-non significant).

Figure14: Effect of samples in serum ALT level.

Figure 15: Effect of samples in serum ALP level.

Figure 16: Effect of samples in serum AST level.

Effect of samples on Lipid parameters

Lipid parameters such as total cholesterol, triglycerides, low density lipoprotein and very low density lipoprotein levels were significantly increased and HDL level was decreased in HFCD control group when compared to normal group. After treatment with formulation altered levels were restored [13]. (Table 6), (Fig. 18-22).

Table6: Effect of Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna on Lipid parameters in HFCD induced obesity.

Groups	Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	Triglycerides (mg/dl)	HDL (mg/dl)	LDL (mg/dl)	VLDL (mg/dl)
Normal	171.3±3.48	135.4± 7.13	88.33±2.03	55.91±2.23	27.09±1.43
Control (HFCD)	242.0±2.89 ^a	296.3±4.91 ^a	41.33±2.60 ^a	141.4±3.59 ^a	59.27±0.98 ^a
Standard	180.0±3.21 ^a	204.0±3.46 ^a	73.67±3.48 ^a	65.53±3.87 ^a	40.80±0.69 ^a
Phytolacca berry (Sample 1)	184.3±3.48 ^a	266.7±6.06 ^c	58.67±3.18 ^c	72.33±2.54 ^a	53.33±1.21 ^c
Stholyantak churna (Sample 2)	174.7±3.76 ^a	254.3±3.53 ^b	65.00±3.46 ^b	59.80±1.86 ^a	50.87±0.71 ^b

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM; (n=6); (p<0.0001, ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparison test). Control vs. Normal. Standard and Test groups vs. Control. (a=***p<0.0001, b=**p<0.001, c=*p<0.05, ns-non significant).

Figure 17: Effect of samples on TC.

Figure 18: Effect of samples on TG.

Figure 19: Effect of samples on HDL.

Figure 20: Effect of samples on LDL.

Figure21: Effect of samples on VLDL in HFCD induced obesity.

DISCUSSION

Obesity is a complex multifactorial chronic disease that develops from an interaction of geno-type and the environment. It involves the integration of social, behavioural, cultural, physiological, metabolic and genetic factors. It substantially raises the risk of morbidity from hypertension, dyslipidaemia, type 2 diabetes, coronary heart disease, stroke, gall bladder disease, osteoarthritis, sleep apnoea, respiratory problems & endometrial, breast, prostate and colon cancers[21]. The present study was under taken to evaluate the efficacy of Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna on high fat cafeteria diet induced obesity in mice. These are ayurvedic and homeopathic formulations, extensively used in the treatment of obesity. This formulations was evaluated for phytochemical studies and results showed the presence of carbohydrates, glycosides, phenols, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, steroids and triterpenoids. Total phenols and flavonoid content was estimated by colorimetric method. Total phenolic content was determined by using the Folin-ciocalteu (FC) reagent method. The total phenolic content of the Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna was found to be 31.16µg/g and 70.39 µg/g calculated as gallic acid equivalent. The total flavonoid content present in samples was determined by aluminium chloride method. The total flavonoid content of the Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna was found to be 12.28µg/g and 41.36µg/g calculated as quercetin equivalent [22]. In order to justify and quantify the presence of phytoconstituents, the samples was subjected to HPTLC screening against marker compounds such as quercetin, rutin, gallic acid as well as they are very effective anti-oxidant marker in various formulations such as hepatoprotectives, anti-obesity ,anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic agents [23]. Polyphenols play beneficial effects on adipose tissue under obese condition by alleviating intracellular oxidative stress, reducing chronic low-grade inflammation, inhibiting adipogenesis and lipogenesis, and suppressing the differentiation of preadipocytes to mature adipocytes. Quercetin have inductive effect on lipolysis, quercetin can also suppress lipogenesis by reducing the incorporation rate of fatty acids into adipocyte triacylglycerols [24]. Consumption of GA is reducing obesity by reduction in oxidative stress. It may alleviate hypertriglyceridemia and fat accumulation through enhancing glycolysis and lipolysis pathways in perirenal adipose tissues [25]. Samples Phytolacca berry showed 0.04% of gallic acid. While Stholyantak churna in aqueous was found to contain 0.47% of gallic acid. Finally Stholyantak churna in methanol showed 0.08% of quercetin and 0.03% of gallic acid (Table 2). In order to validate the efficacy and toxicity, acute toxicity study in animals was performed. In order to determine the extent of toxicity and to fix the dose, acute toxicity studies was carried out for Stholyantak churna according to OECD guidelines 423 in mice with 50mg/kg, 500mg/kg and 2000mg/kg body weight [12]. It was observed that the Stholyantak churna was not lethal to the mice upto 2000mg/kg dose. Body weight and organ weight of the formulations treated groups were significantly reduced in a similar manner of Orlistat treated group while compared to HFCD control group (Table 3, 4). Data of the present study showed significant increase in the levels of hepatic enzymes such as aspartate transaminase (AST), alanine transaminase (ALT) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in HFCD control group (Group II) when compared to group I animals fed with normal chow pellet whereas, the levels of AST, ALT and ALP significantly reduced in the treated groups (Table 5). Evaluation of lipid parameters showed the elevation of TC, TG, LDL, VLDL cholesterol levels and HDL-cholesterol was significantly decreased in the HFCD control group when compared to the normal group. After treatment with formulation, HDL level raised, total cholesterol, triglycerides, low density lipoprotein, very low density lipoprotein levels were decreased in formulation treated groups compared to HFCD control group [13] (Table 6).

CONCLUSION

The present study supports the formulations of Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna have revealed significant anti-obesity activity. The Phytolacca berry and Stholyantak churna was studied for its anti-obesity activity using HFCD induced obesity against Orlistat (50mg/kg) as Standard. Thus the study evidenced that the formulations possesses significant ($p < 0.05$) anti-obesity activity which was apparent with reduction in body weight and organ weight. It moderately reduced hepatic enzymes such as ALT, ALP and AST. Lipid parameters such as total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL and VLDL levels were decreased and HDL level was increased. From the above results, it was concluded that the ayurvedic and homeopathic formulations showed significant anti-obesity activity against high fat cafeteria diet induced obesity. Stholyantak churna possess higher anti-obesity activity than Phytolacca berry. Further experimentation is needed in order to understand the precise mechanism of action of this formulations.

ABBREVIATION USED

Abbreviation	Full name/ Meaning
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
CPCSEA	Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision on Experiments on Animals
IAEC	Institutional Animal Ethical Committee
HFCF	High Fat Cafeteria Diet
BMI	Body Mass Index
GAE	Gallic Acid Equivalent
QE	Quercetin Equivalent
HPTLC	High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography
p.o	per oral
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
HDL	High Density Lipoprotein
LDL	Low Density Lipoprotein
VLDL	Very Low Density Lipoprotein
TG	Triglycerides
TC	Total Cholesterol
AST	Aspartate Transaminase
ALT	Alanine Transaminase
ALP	Alkaline Phosphatase
SOD	Superoxide Dismutase
CAT	Catalase
GPx	Glutathione Peroxidase
GSH	Glutathione
LPO	Lipid Peroxidation

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors thank Chairman and managing Trustee of KMCH College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu for providing necessary facilities for carrying out this work.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors disclose no conflicts of interest for publication of the manuscript.

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